

DETERMINANTS OF THE ASSETS AND LIVELIHOOD DIVERSIFICATION AMONG FISHER-FOLK ON SOCIAL CAPITAL FORMATION IN KAINJI LAKE BASIN OF NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was to determine the assets and livelihood diversification among fisherfolk on social capital formation in the Kainji Lake basin, of Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed in selecting 290 respondents. The questionnaire and interview guide were used to collect primary, and secondary data using journals and textbooks. The result shows that the mean age of the respondents was 42 years, the mean household size was 12 persons and the mean fishing experience was 21 years. Logit regression results on the determinants of social capital formation revealed Pseudo R² of 0.2925 and a chi-square statistic of 109.67 significant at 1% level of probability, indicating the model goodness of fit. Major livelihood sources of the respondents were livestock farming, private business, self-employment and civil servant, ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th, respectively. The mean credit accessed by the fisher-folks due to participating in social capital formation was ₦82,411.79 per month. In contrast, the mean value of assets owned by the respondents in terms of fishing assets, household assets, and livestock assets were ₦627,157.50, ₦753,824.70 and ₦179,072.40, respectively. In conclusion, the fisherfolk in the study areas are involved in other sources of income for survival.

Keywords: Determinants, Social Capital, Asset, Livelihood Diversification

INTRODUCTION

The fishery sector contributes about 50% of the animal protein intake in Nigeria, especially among the resource-poor. The country has an estimated local production of 700,000 metric tonnes with a national demand of over 2.6 million metric tonnes valued at more than \$1.5 billion. Therefore to bridge the gap between demand and supply the country had to import in order to meet the needs of the local populace. It has been reported that Nigeria is the largest fish

consumer in Africa with total consumption of 1.2 million metric tonnes and with Nigeria being Africa's most populous country, it has placed increased demand for protein-based food of which fish represent one type (Ahmed and Vincent, 2014). Due to overfishing and pollution of water bodies, fishing in Nigeria is dwindling which has caused both the artisanal sector and aquaculture industry not to meet the shortfall in the domestic supply of fish, prompting the government to resort to

importing fish to augment domestic consumption thereby leading to the depletion of the country's foreign exchange earnings and social capital on which this study is based (Sangaralingam, 2013). Social capital is an important characteristic of a community, which can influence and be influenced by the flow and stock of other capitals (Emery and Flora, 2006). Social capital is one of the five different types of capital (natural, physical, human, financial and social capital (Pall, 2003).

The decline in the group activities leads to poor outcomes of their fishing activities which reduces their income. The members due to low catch are unable to function in terms of membership contributions to the group through payment of dues, thus could not reap benefits accrued to members that pay dues regularly. There is also a low level of participation in community development which has led to marginalisation of some fisher folks. The fisherfolks pay a very high price for the money they borrow from fish dealers, money-lenders, and equipment and goods suppliers who are the core of the traditional credit system. Fishermen are obliged to sell their catches, to their creditors at pre-determined prices that in most cases are lower than prevailing market prices. Loans are given sometimes in the form of supplies of equipment at prices higher than the prevailing market price. Thus the objectives of this study were to describe the socio-economic characteristics of respondents, identify the assets and livelihood diversification of fisher-folk, and to examine the challenges facing fisher-folks in their fishing activities in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Kainji Lake lies in the savannah region between Lat. 9° 30' and 10° 35' N and between Long. 40° 20' and 4° 40' E, and it was formed after the closure of the river Niger in August 1968 (Balogun and Ibeun, 1995). According to Du-Feu (2001), Kainji Lake has 5000 fishers and the whole Lake has about 286 fishing localities (villages and camps) spread along the shoreline and Island of Kainji Lake. The Lake is divided into three main strata by the Nigerian/German Kainji Lake Fisheries Promotion Project as stratum I, II, and III (Binyotubo and Obhahie, 2006). Stratum I: Represent the Southern part of the lake basin starting from the dam site and terminating at the tip of old Bussa Island. Stratum II: Represent the middle portion of the lake basin starting from where stratum I terminates. It is the largest basin of the Lake covering about 65% of the surface area with a width of 24km. Stratum III: Represents the uppermost part of the Lake and terminates at Nigeria's border with Niger Republic. Most of the fishing communities (61%) are located in Niger State and 39% in Kebbi State. The fisherfolk in the area are mainly Bussawa, Kambiri, Gugawa and Ijaws.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

The population of this study was the artisanal fisher-folk households in fishing villages around the Kainji Lake areas in Niger and Kebbi States. Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in the selection of respondents for this study. In stage one, three Local Government Areas (Magama, Agwara and Borgu) and two Local Government Areas (Ngaski and Yauri) were purposively selected from

Niger and Kebbi States, respectively. Stage two involved proportionate sampling of the fishing communities by 50% in the two States which are 51 in total to get 26 communities. In the third stage, the total registered fisher-folk households engaged in fishing activities were obtained from Niger and Kebbi States Bureau of Statistics in 2013, respectively, as the sampling frame. Stage four involved proportionate

sampling of fisher-folk households based on the sample frame obtained from each of the fishing communities in the five Local Government Areas selected using the Yamanne (1967) formula as adapted by Agu and Udoh (2012) to obtain a total of 290 respondents used for the study. The Yamanne equation is mathematically expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size, N = Finite population, e = limit of tolerable error (i.e. level of precision (0.05))

Table 1: Sampling Procedures of the Respondents

Selected States	LGAs	Fishing Communities (50%)	Sample Frame	Sample Fisher-folks
Niger	Magama	8 (4)	175	48
	Agwara	10 (5)	179	49
	Borgu	11 (6)	282	78
Kebbi	Ngaski	12 (6)	264	73
	Yauri	10 (5)	152	42
Total	5	51 (26)	1052	290

Source: Niger and Kebbi States Bureau of Statistics (2013)

Data Collection

Primary data used for this study were collected using a structured questionnaire complemented with an interview schedule. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents with the help of trained enumerators and ADP field officers who are in contact with the fishing communities to collect information on their socio-economic characteristics, level and source of social capital formation, determinants of social capital formation and other

parameters for the study. However, other relevant information was obtained from published literature such as textbooks, bulletins, newspapers, magazines, journals, conference papers and the Internet among others.

Data Analysis

Data collected were subjected to analysis using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Objectives i, ii, and iii were achieved using descriptive statistics such

as frequency distribution, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, while the inferential statistic used were: Logit regression, factor analysis, farm budgeting technique, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Chi-square.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-Economic Characteristics

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents under consideration include age, sex, marital status, household size, years of farming experience, level of education, farm size, and respondents' annual income. Table 2 revealed that the majority (69.8%) of the respondents were

within the age range of 31-50 years with a mean age of 42 years. This implies that the respondents were in their mid-age where they could actively participate in social capital formation. It is assumed that younger fisher folks are more likely to be involved in social capital formation due to their innovativeness and willingness to engage in new ideas that could change their economic status for better livelihood. These findings are in line with the assertion of Million and Belay (2004) that most active-age farmers can easily key into new technology. Similarly, Ani (2007) stressed that the innovators are mostly in their active years.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on their socio-economic characteristics (n=290)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age (years)			
< 31	34	11.7	42.0
31 – 40	94	32.4	
41 – 50	109	37.6	
51 – 60	44	15.2	
> 60	9	3.1	
Sex			
Male	276	95.2	
Female	14	4.8	
Education level			
Non-formal	172	59.3	
Quranic	81	27.9	
Primary	20	6.9	
Secondary	17	5.9	
Household (number)			
< 6	41	14.1	12.0
6 – 10	58	20.0	
11 – 15	144	49.7	
16 – 20	30	10.3	
21 – 25	14	4.8	
> 25	3	1.1	
Experience			
< 11	48	16.6	22.0
–			

11 – 20	109	37.6
21 – 30	65	22.4
31 – 40	58	20.0
> 40	10	3.4
Primary occupation		
Fishing	283	97.6
Trading	7	2.4
Secondary occupation*		
Farming	85	29.3
Trading	14	4.8
Civil servant	55	19.0
Private	85	29.3
Craft	85	29.3
Ownership of canoe		
Yes	214	73.8
No	76	26.2

Sources: Field survey, 2016

*Multiple responses

Sex of respondents

Table 2 showed that the majority (95.2%) of the respondents in the study area were males, while 4.8% of the respondents were females. This indicates that males were more engaged in fishing than females. Males dominate fishing activities because of the laborious nature of fishing operations. This finding is in line with the work of Adeleke (2013) who posited that fishing activities involve more males than females because of the strength, standard times required and various risks of the fishing job. Also about 59.3% of the respondents in the study area had no formal education and 27.3% of the respondents acquired quaranic education, 6.9% of the respondents acquired primary education and 5.9% of the respondents acquired secondary education. This implies that the majority of the respondents did not acquire formal education, thus low literacy level. This development is unhealthy for social capital formation in the study area, as education enhanced the formation of social capital. It was revealed

that the majority (69.7%) of the respondents in the study area had a household size of between 6 – 15 persons with a mean household size of 12 persons. This implies that the respondents in the study area have relatively large household sizes. These findings agreed with Johnson (2009) who stressed that farmers with large households are more likely to engage in more income-beneficiary activities such as social capital formation. Table 2 revealed that the majority (60.0%) of the respondents in the study area had between 11 – 30 years of farming experience with a mean fishing experience of 21 years. This implies that the respondents in the study area had been involved in fishing activities for many years. The number of years spent indicates the practical knowledge acquired by the fisherfolks in fishing activities. This result agrees with the findings of Nwaru *et al.* (2006) who stated that the number of years spent in fish farming gives an indication of the practical knowledge acquired on how to cope with inherent fish production, processing and marketing

problems. Experience in fishing is expected to influence respondents' involvement in social capital formation. Table 2 revealed that the majority (97.6%) of the respondents in the study area were fishermen and 2.4% of the respondents were into fishing as a secondary occupation. This indicates that the majority of the respondents in the study area were fishermen which could be due to the fact that they live along the riverine area where fish is the source of their livelihood. This is in agreement with the work of Nwabueze (2010) who reported that fishing practices take place in remote localities which contributed significantly to food security, income generation and improved standards of living of the rural populace. Table 2 revealed that 29.3% of the respondents indicated farming as their secondary occupation and 29.3% were craftsmen. Also, 19.0% of the respondents in the study area were civil servants and 4.8% were traders. These findings showed that most of the respondents have secondary occupations which could influence their involvement in social capital formation in the study area. Those who are civil servants and spend many hours at their place of work could hardly find it easy to participate in social capital formation. Table 3.1 revealed that the majority (73.8%) of the respondents in the study area owned canoes for fishing activities and 26.2% of the respondents did not own canoes. This implies that the majority of the respondent owned their personal canoe for fishing activities in the study area which could help raise their fish

catch and in turn, increase their income for better livelihood. This could enhance social capital formation as most of the respondents will be able to generate income which in turn raise their social status.

Institutional variables of respondents

The institutional variables accessed by the respondents in the study area include cooperative membership, extension contact, and access to credit which are presented in Table 3, revealed that 43.1% of the respondents belong to cooperative societies and 56.9% did not belong to cooperative societies. This implies that half of the respondents did not belong to cooperative societies which could have a negative effect on social capital formation in the study area. However, 36.2% of the respondents had been in a cooperative within the range of 1 – 10 years, while only a few (2.4%) had been members of cooperatives within the range of 11 – 20 years. Also, 4.5% of the respondents had been members of cooperatives for more than 20 years with a mean years of 9. The number of years spent in cooperatives is expected to boost farmers' knowledge and enhance their involvement in social capital formation. However, in terms of the number of cooperative societies the respondent belongs to, 37.9% belong to two cooperative societies, 3.8%, belong to four cooperative societies and 0.7% belong to more than four cooperative societies in the study area (Abiona, 2010).

Table 3 Distribution of respondents based on their institutional variables (n = 290)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Membership of cooperative			
Yes	125	43.1	
No	165	56.9	
Years in cooperative			
1-10	105	36.2	9
11-20	7	2.4	
>20	13	4.5	
Number of cooperative			
Two	110	37.9	
Three	2	0.7	
Four	2	0.7	
Five	11	3.8	
Time of cooperative meeting			
Weekly	10	3.5	
Monthly	14	4.8	
Bi-monthly	90	31.0	
Quarterly	11	3.8	
Benefits from cooperative			
Access to loan	44	15.2	
Purchase of fishing tools	54	18.6	
Market of fishing product	27	9.3	
Extension contact			
Yes	172	59.3	
No	118	40.7	
Number of visits			
1 – 2 times	27	9.3	
3 – 4 times	135	46.6	
> 4	10	3.4	
Access to credit			
Yes	149	51.4	
No	141	48.6	
Constraints to credit*			
High interest rate	97	33.4	
Insufficient credit	77	26.6	
Collateral security	51	17.6	
Delaying in getting credit	46	15.9	

Source: Field survey, 2016

*multiple responses

In terms of frequency of meeting, most (31.0%) of the respondents met on bi-weekly basis, while few (4.8%) of the respondents met on a monthly basis, 3.4% of the respondents met on a quarterly basis and 3.5% of the respondents met on weekly basis. Meetings are very vital in social capital formation because that is where the issues regarding their well-being are always discussed by the fisherfolks. Moreover, concerning people who participated in cooperative societies, 18.6% of the respondents benefited from cooperatives for the purchase of their fishing inputs, 15.2% of the respondents benefited from accessing loan through cooperatives and 9.3% benefited from cooperative societies as it helped them to market their fish products. The benefits derived from cooperatives could be major determinants of fisherfolks' involvement in social capital formation and it is expected to enhance their fishing activities.

Table 3 showed that 59.3% of respondents had access to extension services and 40.7% of the respondents had no access to extension. Extension contact has been proven to have a positive effect on the adoption of improved technologies. Access to extension services is expected to influence the adoption of fishing technologies which could, in turn, enhance participation in social capital formation. Yaron *et al.* (2012) reported that extension contact can counterbalance the negative effect of lack of formal education in the overall decision to adopt some technologies. Furthermore, the result revealed that 46.6% of the respondents in the study area were visited 3 – 4 times by extension agents annually, while 9.3% of the respondents were visited by extension agents 1-2 times annually and 3.8% of the respondents were visited by extension

agents more than 4 times annually.

In Table 3, more than half (51.4%) of the respondents in the study area had access to credit and 48.6% of them did not have access to credit. Credit is a catalyst for increased agricultural production and technology adoption especially fishing technologies. Availability of credit becomes imperative for improving and enhancing income. Akudugu *et al.* (2012) stressed that post-harvest loss among farmers was attributed to a lack of access to credit that will bring about affordable technologies. The result further revealed that high interest rate (33.4%), followed by insufficient credit (26.6%), lack of collateral security (17.6%), and delays in getting credit (15.9%) were constraints identified in accessing credit in the study area. Access to credit had a positive coefficient (0.93) and was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) implying that access to credit had a direct relationship with social capital formation. This implies that the more the fisher folks have access to credit, the higher the probability of the respondents participating in social capital formation. In most cases, the rural poor often find it difficult to access formal credit and insurance market mechanisms and therefore rely more on informal reciprocal arrangements through social capital formation. They do contribute and benefit from the effective social safety nets generated by social capital. This is in agreement with Karlan *et al.* (2009) who reported that households with poor access to a formal credit market may constantly invest in social capital to secure access to informal credit sources because social capital improves credit market accessibility through social enforcement and social collateral mechanisms.

Access to the market had a positive

coefficient (0.73) and was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) implying that market access had a direct relationship with social capital formation. This implies that increased access to the market increases the probability of social capital formation. This shows that access to market enhances the formation of social capital formation that facilitates information sharing. This finding is in agreement with the work of Katungi *et al.* (2012) who posited that poor access to market also means reduced physical access to markets and it obliges people to be more interdependent, thus possibly increasing the incentive for social capital formation.

Cooperative membership had positive coefficient (1.49) and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) implying that cooperative membership had direct relationships with social capital formation. This shows that cooperative membership increases the probability of the respondents participating in social capital formation which is in line with the *a priori* expectations. An individual acquires social capital through participation in informal networks, registered organizations, associations of different kinds and social movements. Membership in an organization can stimulate investment in social networks. Cooperative societies play various roles in enhancing social capital. It gives the cooperative members the impression that the contributors will devote his/her resources to community development. This is in line with Shoji *et al.* (2012) who reported that villages with more social capital are more likely to enjoy better public services, adopt advanced agricultural practices, and participate in communal activities, and that these in turn increase individual income.

Information sources of the respondents had

a positive coefficient (0.36) and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) implying a direct relationship. This shows that access to good sources of information coupled with timely and adequate information dissemination will have a positive effect on social capital formation in the study area. This finding is also in line with Katungi *et al.* (2012) who posited that access to communication facilities could enhance information sharing and increase the chance of participating in organizations / social networks. The information which may be gained through social capital could likely be useful in policy design and decision-making.

Furthermore, the mean value of assets owned by the fisherfolks in terms of fishing assets, household assets and livestock assets were ₦627,157.50, ₦753,824.70 and ₦179,072.40, respectively. This implies that the fisher-folks were at disposal of various assets covering fishing, livestock and household assets as revealed by their mean value. The net worth of individual fisher-folk depends on the types of asset own and the value for it. This finding is in agreement with the work of Winter *et al.* (2009) who posited that the value and use of an asset depend not only on the quantity owned but also on the ownership status of the asset. In addition, the mean income of the fisher-folks was ₦417,451.50. This implies that, higher income from fishing activities will encourage social capital formation as fisher-folks could easily interact and benefit one another in terms of resources sharing. According to Ajayi *et al.* (2016), long term concern about the ability of smallholder farmers is to generate sufficient income for their increasing households' daily needs.

Fishing assets of the respondents

Table 4 showed the list of the fishing assets of the respondents in the study area. Fishing assets can be categorized into three which are fish catch assets, fish processing and accessories. However, in the course of this study these assets were grouped together. In Table 3.15, majority (97.9%) of the respondents in the study area owned gills nets, 96.6% of the respondents owned fish smoking kiln and 93.8% of the respondents owned motorised canoe ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd, respectively. Other fishing assets owned by the respondents in the study area include cast nets (93.5%), outboard engine (92.1%), fishing gear (91.4%), non-motorised canoe/boat (91.2%), fish pond (88.6%), generator (88.3%), pack of batteries (78.6%), torch light (77.6%), harvesting trap (76.9%), fish traps (73.1%), seiling nets (63.1%), refrigerator (55.9%), boots (55.5%), tube well (50.0%) and warehouse (3.1%) as the least fishing assets owned by the respondents. Fishing assets are very vital because it determines the involvement in social capital formation among the fisher-folks in the study area. This finding is in agreement with Ifejika *et al.* (2012) in their work physical assets ownership of fisher-folks in fishing communities of Kainji Lake, Nigeria reported that dominant fishing assets owned by the fisher-folks were fishing net and fishing canoe. Fish drying net and solar tent dryer are also assets for fish processing that use sun energy, while other fishing assets are fishing nets, speed engine boat, hook & line, deep freezer and accessories like weighing balance, boots, touch light and batteries.

Moreover, majority (90.7%) of the respondents owned wood/charcoal stove, 77.7% of the respondents owned kerosine stove and 63.8% of the respondents owned fan ranked 4th, 5th and 6th, respectively among the household assets owned by the respondents. The least household assets owned by the respondents are plot of land (25.9%), electrical appliances (17.2%) and phone set (13.5%) ranked 7th, 8th and 9th, respectively. This implies that the fisher-folks acquired physical assets that could enhance their standard of living through social capital formation. Household assets net worth or wealth is an important defining factor of economic well-being which in time of hardship, they are additional source of income to help pay household expenses. However, the net worth of a household depends on the types of asset own and the value for it. This finding is in agreement with Muyanga *et al.* (2010) who reported that households can rely on available assets to smoothen consumption in times of stress and shock. However, Winter *et al.* (2009) argued that the value and use of an asset depend not only on the quantity owned but also on the ownership status of the asset.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents according to their fishing assets

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Gill nets	284	97.9	1 st
Fish smoking kiln	281	96.9	2 nd
Motorised canoe/boat	272	93.8	3 rd
Cast nets	271	93.5	4 th
Outboard engine	267	92.1	5 th
Fish gear	265	91.4	6 th
Non motorised canoe/boat	266	91.2	7 th
Fish pond	257	88.6	8 th
Generator	256	88.3	9 th
Pack of batteries	228	78.6	10 th
Torch light	225	77.6	11 th
Harvesting trap	223	76.9	12 th
Fish traps	212	73.1	13 th
Seiline nets	183	63.1	14 th
Refrigerator	162	55.9	15 th
Boots	161	55.5	16 th
Tube well	145	50.0	17 th
Warehouse	9	3.1	18 th

Source: Field survey, 2016***Multiple responses**

However, one of the major central focuses of social capital formation was to enhance social networking that will increase fisher-folk's output and income as well as raise their socio-economic status. Fishing assets are very vital indicators of fisher-folks involvement in social capital formation in the study area. In Table 5, fish smoking kilns, fish ponds, fish gear and gill net with mean value of 4.34, 3.07, 2.72 and 2.31, respectively were the main fishing assets owned and benefited by the fisher-folks as a

result of social capital formation. This implies that each of the fisher-folk has four number of fish smoking kiln, three fish ponds, about three fish gears and two gill nets. However, the least fishing asset owned by the fisher-folks as a result of involvement in social capital formation was warehouse with mean value of 0.06, implying that two out of every twenty-nine fisher-folks owned a warehouse where they could stock fish and fish products.

Table 5: Indicators of social capital formation benefits based on fishing assets (n=290)

Fishing assets	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Non-motorized canoe/boat	1.61	0.88	1.00	9.00
Motorised canoe/boat	1.41	0.68	1.00	3.00
Gill nets	2.31	1.28	1.00	10.00
Seiline nets	0.77	0.80	1.00	7.00
Cast nets	1.48	1.01	1.00	6.00
Outboard engine	1.07	0.60	1.00	6.00
Refrigerator	0.58	0.54	1.00	3.00
Fish traps	1.34	1.64	1.00	9.00
Pack of batteries	1.39	3.29	1.00	50.00
Boots	0.68	0.71	1.00	4.00
Generator	1.41	0.78	1.00	7.00
Warehouse	0.06	0.33	1.00	2.00
Harvesting trap	1.46	1.39	1.00	10.00
Fishing smoking kiln	4.34	5.27	1.00	31.00
Fish gear	2.72	1.97	1.00	15.00
Fish pond	3.07	4.57	1.00	30.00
Tube well	0.67	1.18	1.00	7.00
Torch light	1.46	1.84	1.00	10.00

Source: Field survey, 2016

Table 6 revealed the distribution of respondents based on different social group formations in the study area. It revealed that 24.1% of the respondents belong to Aldaji fishermen social group, followed by 23.4% of the respondents who belongs to Yunna fishermen association and 22.8% belongs to Monnai fisheries multipurpose. Fisher-folks groups, such as associations or cooperatives create social relations that enable individuals to achieve goals that individuals are not able to achieve. They benefit from economies of scale when sharing information on how to access resource inputs, and rely on help of one another to meet the needs of friends or people they can trust. Membership into

fisher-folks groups further enables individuals to have access to capacity building such as training and study tours, and to information pertaining to new technologies. The groups or other local-level community with formal or informal structures shape norms, such as extent of trust, abiding by by-laws, settling conflicts, cooperation among members, giving gifts or exchanging items, as well as the extent of financial contributions toward group activities or collective community problems. However, small groups are more cohesive than large groups as they tend to have high performance goals making them to be more productive (Mayunga, 2007).

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to Social Group (n=290)

Farmer's group	Frequency*	Percentages
Monnai fisheries multipurpose	66	22.8
Monnai Fisheries Youth development	44	15.2
Yunna fishermen association	68	23.4
Musawa Fishermen multipurpose cooperative societies	50	17.2
Monnai Women Fishing Business Association	32	11.0
Monnai fish pond owner's association	24	8.3
Iraishe Fishermen Cooperatives Society	42	14.5
Aldaji fishermen	70	24.1
Awuru fishery	64	22.1
Ellae fishermen cooperatives	30	10.3
Majovo fishing	52	17.9
Danbaba Cooperative Fishermen Society	38	13.1
Bongo Seriki fishermen	56	19.3
Imman Fishermen Cooperative Society	45	15.5

Source: Field survey, 2016 *Multiple responses

Constraints faced by Respondents

A number of constraints were identified by the respondents and ranked according to their severity as presented in Table 8. All the constraints were found to be severe which includes scarcity of fishing gears with mean value of $X = 2.98$ and ranked 1st, this might be caused by the inability of farmers to purchase fishing gear. This was followed by inadequate participation in group activities ($X = 2.88$) ranked 2nd, this constraint might be because fish farmers were not adequately carried along with the various group activities that would have influenced their participation. Moreover, age of fisher-folk had mean value of 2.87 and ranked 3rd, implying that age is very vital because it plays important roles in the adoption of new technologies. Age influences the way an individual discounts the future and lowers the propensity to invest in social capital. The effect of age on participation in organizations is likely to depend on the type of organization. This is in line with Katungi *et al.* (2012) who

posited that age may increase the likelihood of participation in social interactions that require trust. Other constraints faced by respondents in the study area include disease infestation and lack of trust in government institutions ($X = 2.86$) ranked 4th as most fisher-folk did not have absolute trust in government institutions operating within their vicinities, and irregular membership and inaccessibility of water/river ($X = 2.85$) which ranked 6th among the constraints of the respondents. Disease occurrence is a serious challenge to the fisher-folks as it leads to decrease in income and substantial loss in fish catch. The self-reinforcing nature of social capital may also enhance or inhibit participation in organizations/social networks. The expected utility from membership in a local organization/social network also depends on the social, economic and institutional environment (Glaeser *et al.*, 2001).

Table 8. Perceived challenges faced by the respondents in fishing activities (n=290)

Variable	Very severe	Severe	Not severe	Sum	Mean	Rank	Remarks
Scarcity of fishing gears	267 (92.1%)	28 (9.7%)	8 (2.8%)	865	2.98	1 st	Severe
Inadequate participation in group	268 (92.4%)	12 (4.1%)	10 (3.4%)	838	2.88	2 nd	Severe
Age of fisherfolk affects social formation	263 (90.7%)	17 (5.9%)	10 (3.4%)	833	2.87	3 rd	Severe
Lack of trust in government institutions	260 (89.7%)	19 (6.6%)	11 (3.8%)	829	2.86	4 th	Severe
Disease infestation	254 (87.6%)	30 (10.3%)	6 (2.1%)	824	2.86	4 th	Severe
Irregular membership	254 (87.6%)	28 (9.7%)	8 (2.8%)	826	2.85	6 th	Severe
Inaccessibility of water/river	258 (89.0%)	20 (6.9%)	12 (4.1%)	826	2.85	6 th	Severe
Inadequate storage facilities	249 (85.9%)	36 (12.4%)	5 (1.7%)	824	2.84	8 th	Severe
Climate variability	249 (85.9%)	36 (12.4%)	5 (1.7)	824	2.84	8 th	Severe
Problem of competition	169 (68.3%)	110 (37.9%)	11 (3.8%)	738	2.54	10 th	Severe

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 8, shows inadequate storage facilities and climate variability ($\bar{X} = 2.84$) ranked 8th, which could be due to post-harvest handling during transportation, marketing and preservation. Various methods of fish preservation are labourious and time-consuming to small-scale farmers this constraint is well pronounced in Nigeria and has resulted in severe loss of agricultural produce. FAO (2010) posited that the most common causes of losses are due to inadequate handling and processing methods, lack of knowledge and skills amongst producers, as well as poor access to infrastructure, equipment and services such as water, ice, electricity, roads and credit are all fundamental. Problem of competition ($\bar{X} = 2.54$) ranked 10th is another constraint faced by the respondents.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of this study, it can be

concluded that the fisher-folks who engaged in social capital formation were in their mid-age and primarily into fishing activities. Explanatory variables such as age, household size, access to credit and market, cooperative membership and information sources were the major determinants of effectiveness of social capital formation in the study area. The major fishery assets owned by fisher folk are gill nets, smoking kiln, motorized canoes, cast-nets, outboard engine, fishing gears, non-motorized canoe/boat, touch fish high pond, generator, battery, trap) sailing net and refrigerator. Most of the respondents engaged in livelihood diversification apart from fishing activities, this have helped to enhance the livelihood of the fisherfolks.

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